

ÖRGÜTSEL TÜKENMİŞLİK: BİR LİTERATÜR ÇALIŞMASI¹

ORGANİZATİONAL BURNOUT: A LITERATURE STUDY

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ÖZET

Tükenmişlik bireylerin yaşadıkları olumsuz durumlar sonucunda yaşadığı güç ve enerji kaybı nedeniyle ortaya çıkan olumsuz bir durumdur. Tükenmişlik duygusu her bireyde farklı tepkilere ve durumlara sebep olabilen olumsuz bir durumdur. Tükenmişlik durumu literatürde tükenmişlik sendromu olarak geçmektedir. Tükenmişlik sendromu yüz-yüze karşılıklı ilişkilerin yoğun olduğu örgütlerde daha sık yaşanan sendromdur. Tükenmişlik bireylerde bıkkınlık, yaptığı işe yabancılaşma, iş performansının düşmesi, işten ayrılma niyetinin oluşması, işine olan bağlılığının azalması gibi olumsuz düşünceleri ortaya çıkartmaktadır. Örgütlerde tükenmişlik duygusal tükenme, duyarsızlaşma ve bireysel başarıyı etkileyen faktörler boyutu olmak üzere üç önemli boyuttan oluşmaktadır. Günümüzde global dünyada örgütlerde yaşanan yoğun rekabet ortamları bireyler arasındaki ilişkilerin zedelenerek azalmasına, bireylerin teknolojik gelişmelere uyumunun zayıflamasına sebep olmaktadır. Örgütlerde tükenmişliğe sebep olan faktörler arasında en önemlileri; bireysel özellikler, bireylerin beklentileri, yaşam biçimleri, örgüt içinde destekleyici yönetim anlayışının olmaması gibidir. Örgütlerdeki çalışma şartları ve bu şartların çalışanlarda yarattığı stres, örgüt içindeki iletişimsizlik, yönetimin çalışanlarından aşırı beklenti içinde olması, yaşanan belirsizlikler, elverişsiz çalışma koşulları, çıkar çatışmaları ve aşırı iş yükü gibi durumlar tükenmişliğin örgütsel nedenleridir. Örgütlerde bireylerin yaşadığı tükenmişlik durumu çalışanların yaptıkları işleri savsaklaması, örgüte karşı ilgisizlik ve güvensizlik, doyumsuzluk, işi bırakma eğilimi, performans düşüklüğü gibi sonuçlara sebep olmaktadır. Örgütlerde tükenmişlik ile mücadele etme sürecinde örgüt yönetimlerinin çalışanlarının bireysel kararlarına olanak vermesi, adil bir ödüllendirme sisteminin oluşturulması, çalışanların karar verme süreçlerine dâhil edilmesi, yapılan işlerin etkili biçimde gözden geçirilmesi gerekmektedir. Örgüt içinde çalışanların görev yeri değişikliklerinin yapılması ve kariyer fırsatlarının değerlendirilmesi, hizmet içi eğitimlerin gerçekleştirilmesi diğer önemli konulardır. Bu çalışmada örgütsel tükenmişlik kavramı sebep ve sonuçlarıyla birlikte detaylı olarak ele alınmış ve literatürde yapılmış olan çalışmalara yer verilmiştir.

Anahtar kelimeler: Tükenmişlik, örgütsel tükenmişlik, tükenmişlik sendromu

ABSTRACT

Burnout is a negative situation that occurs due to the loss of power and energy experienced by individuals as a result of negative situations they experience. Burnout is a negative situation that can cause different reactions and situations in each individual. Burnout is referred to as burnout syndrome in the literature. Burnout syndrome is more common in organizations where face-to-face mutual relations are intense. Burnout brings out negative

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thoughts such as boredom, alienation from the work, decreased work performance, intention to leave the job, and decreased commitment to the job. Burnout in organizations consists of three important dimensions: emotional exhaustion, depersonalization and factors affecting individual success. Today, intense competition in organizations in the global world causes the relationships between individuals to be damaged and reduced, and the adaptation of individuals to technological developments to weaken. Among the factors that cause burnout in organizations, the most important ones are individual characteristics, expectations of individuals, lifestyles, lack of a supportive management approach within the organization. Organizational causes of burnout include working conditions in organizations and the stress these conditions create in employees, miscommunication within the organization, excessive expectations of management from employees, uncertainties, unfavorable working conditions, conflicts of interest and excessive workload. The burnout situation experienced by individuals in organizations causes results such as employees' neglect of their work, apathy and distrust towards the organization, dissatisfaction, tendency to quit the job, and low performance. In the process of combating burnout in organizations, it is necessary for organizational managements to allow individual decisions of employees, to create a fair reward system, to include employees in decision-making processes, and to review the work done effectively. Other important issues are changing the workplace of employees within the organization, evaluating career opportunities, and providing in-service trainings. In this study, the concept of organizational burnout is discussed in detail with its causes and consequences and the studies in the literature are included.

Key words: Burnout, organizational burnout, burnout syndrome

1. INTRODUCTION

First introduced into management literature in the 1970s, burnout has become a topic of considerable interest in the field of organizational behavior today. Burnout manifests itself in individuals as a decline in psychological and physical energy, emotional and perceptual disturbances, and a resulting disengagement from work. Burnout has been defined in various ways in the literature. According to Dolgun (2016), burnout refers to the inadequacies and problems individuals experience in coping with stress in their personal and professional lives (Dolgun, 2012). The most widely accepted definition in recent foreign and domestic studies is that proposed by Maslach. Maslach defines burnout as emotional exhaustion, numbness, and a strong desire for success observed in individuals who have intense relationships with others due to a heavy work load (Budak and Sürvegül, 2005). As can be understood from the definition, burnout is more common among individuals working in direct service sectors who have intense relationships with others. This is because the high number of one-on-one interactions and the heavy workload in these sectors have a negative impact on employees. In this study, the concept of burnout is examined in detail, and a detailed literature review is conducted, touching on the negative effects of burnout in organizations and how these effects can be prevented.

2. THE CONCEPTS OF BURNOUT AND ORGANIZATIONAL BURNOUT

The concept of burnout, known in English as “burnout,” is a negative situation that arises in organizations where individuals work for long periods of time in environments with high emotional demands, resulting in physical exhaustion and negative attitudes toward other employees and management. The concept of burnout was first introduced in Grene's 1961 novel “An Incident of Burnout” (Derin and Demirel, 2011). The concept was first addressed and defined in management literature in Freudenberger's 1974 study. In this study, the concept of burnout is defined as the inability of individuals working in the healthcare sector to

fulfill their own desires and the depletion of their internal motivation when they experience failure, wear and tear, loss of strength, and loss of energy in their work environment (Siliğ, 2003). Freudenberger described burnout as a “professional hazard” in the results of his study (Suran & Sheridan, 1985).

2.1. Causes of Burnout

Burnout is the emotional and physical exhaustion experienced by organizational employees due to negative situations they encounter in their work environment. Individuals' burnout states, i.e., their responses, may vary. However, in general, burnout emerges one year after individuals begin working in an organization, and they begin to experience these negative emotions (Erdoğan, 2018). In his study (2016), Kapusuz categorizes the factors causing burnout in organizations into two groups: personal factors and organizational factors (Kapusuz, 2016):

a. Personal Factors: These include demographic characteristics such as age, gender, and educational status of organizational employees, as well as factors such as length of service, lifestyle, expectations regarding social security and social support, and personal expectations.

b. Organizational Factors: These include employees' working conditions, differences with other colleagues, lack of communication within the organization, pressure from organizational management, conflicts and contradictions between organizational values and personal values, unfavorable working conditions, and stress and pressure experienced by the individual in the workplace.

2.2. Stages of Burnout

According to Edellwich, there are four stages of burnout. These stages are listed below (Kaçmaz, 2005):

a. The stage of the formation and increase of enthusiasm and idealistic excitement (These are feelings that begin after individuals have worked in an organization for one year. During this period, individuals are committed to their work and profession, and their expectations of the organization will be high.)

b. The stagnation stage (Immediately after the idealistic enthusiasm stage, the individual begins to experience a decline in energy levels. The reason for this is that the individual, who was in a state of idealistic enthusiasm due to excessive expectations, has not had their expectations met by the organization and has experienced disappointment. As a result, the individual will begin to distance themselves from their work and become disengaged.)

c. Blockage stage (At this stage, the person feels that they are being blocked in their work environment. As a result, their self-confidence begins to decline and they start to feel inadequate. They begin to question their work and think that it is not suitable for them.)

d. Indifference stage (Apathy) (In the apathy stage, individuals begin to think that they are too late to improve themselves in their work and avoid taking risks. At this stage, individuals begin to arrive late to work, and their desire to escape and leave their jobs increases.

2.3. Signs of Burnout

Although burnout is thought to manifest itself in individuals through depression, increased anxiety, and stress, it actually emerges as a hidden process that develops and progresses within individuals. Studies have shown that burnout manifests itself in individuals through psychological, physical, and behavioral symptoms (Acar, 2016). The physical symptoms of burnout include insomnia, increased alcohol and cigarette consumption, stomach and heart problems, and constant illness. Behavioral symptoms include individuals becoming

disengaged from their work and organization, not wanting to go to work and hating their job, constant anger, withdrawal and forgetfulness, negative mood swings, and loss of self-confidence. Psychological factors include disappointment, hopelessness, increased family problems, insomnia, constant anxiety and worry, and feeling alienated from everything in both personal and professional life (Ardıç & Polatçı, 2008).

2.4. Measures to be Taken to Prevent Burnout

Burnout causes individuals to procrastinate or neglect their duties at work, dissatisfaction with all aspects of the organization, an increased tendency to quit their jobs, and a decline in performance. These negative situations reduce the effectiveness and efficiency of the organization's activities and even cause an increase in work accidents (Çapulcuoğlu, 2012). There are measures that organizations must take to eliminate the negative effects of burnout. These measures are individual and organizational measures (Güllüce, 2006):

a. Individual Measures: These are the measures individuals should take to avoid burnout. These include engaging in social activities, traveling, resting, paying attention to nutrition and health, trying to think optimistically rather than pessimistically, creating a new work program for themselves within the organization, leaving work at work and not bringing it into their personal lives, and participating in conferences and training seminars within or outside the organization.

b. Organizational Measures: These include the organization's management giving employees more say and ensuring their participation in organizational processes, establishing a fair reward system within the organization, providing employees with the necessary support regarding organizational commitment and teamwork, clearly distributing roles and responsibilities within the organization to prevent conflicts between employees, and providing in-service training.

3. LITERATURE REVIEW ON ORGANIZATIONAL BURNOUT

There are numerous studies on the concept of burnout in organizations, i.e., organizational burnout. This section reviews the studies conducted in the literature. Maslach and colleagues (2001) stated in their study that the individual stress dimension of burnout is explained by the concept of emotional exhaustion and that, based on this, burnout can cause a decrease in individuals' emotional and physical resources and activities (Maslach et al., 2001). Another important issue to consider here is desensitization, in addition to emotional exhaustion. Cynicism among organizational employees refers to the individual becoming indifferent and uncaring toward other employees and the organizational processes they work in (Wright and Douglas, 1997). The onset of cynicism among organizational employees as a result of burnout will bring with it the fear of failure in the work being done.

In the study conducted by Öztürk (2019), a study was conducted on university staff. In this study, the mobbing perceptions and professional burnout levels of university academic staff were examined in terms of demographic characteristics such as age, gender, title and marital status. As a result; It was determined that there was no significant change in the effects of mobbing perception on burnout levels of academic staff according to demographic characteristics (Öztürk, 2019). In the study conducted by Çalışkan and Özkan (2020), the effect of organizational commitment on burnout perception and the mediating role of job satisfaction in this effect were examined. In the study conducted, people working in the health

sector were examined and as a result, it was concluded that organizational commitment significantly affected burnout. Accordingly, it was said that there was a negatively significant relationship between organizational commitment and burnout (Çalışkan and Özkan, 2020)

Özutku (2019) examined the effects of employees' burnout dimensions on their physical health status and life balance. In this study, a study was conducted on bank employees. As a result; it was stated that there was no significant relationship between the education levels of employees and emotional exhaustion and desensitization, there was no significant difference between desensitization and the ages of the employees, but; the desensitization levels of young employees were slightly higher than those of older employees (Özutku, 2019). Faiz (2019) focused on the effect of excessive workload and burnout syndrome on the intention to leave the job. The study examined a certain number of people working in the food, ready-made clothing and information sectors. As a result; it was determined that there was a positive relationship between excessive workload, emotional exhaustion and desensitization and the intention to leave the job (Faiz, 2019). In the study conducted by Kulualp and Sarı (2019), a certain number of employees of a public institution were examined and it was investigated what kind of psychological state burnout syndrome was an indicator of in these people. The study examined the emotional control, work relationships, social norms, time management, negative emotional states and emotional exhaustion issues in the workplaces where the public employees worked. As a result, it has been determined that employees have difficulty complying with the rules of the workplace they work in when they feel psychologically bad and are reluctant to fulfill their duties. Experiencing emotional exhaustion will increase the burnout of employees and cause job dissatisfaction, fatigue, exhaustion and emotional breakdown (Kulualp and Sarı, 2019).

In Demir's study (2019), a certain number of working teachers were examined. The effects of leader-member interaction on the negative attitudes, burnout and stress levels of the teachers were examined in the study. As a result; the lack of a good leader-member interaction will negatively affect employees and cause increases in their burnout and stress levels (Demir, 2019). Sivrikaya conducted a study on the burnout and work-related tension levels of employees in his study (2019). In this study, a certain number of healthcare workers in a healthcare institution were examined. As a result; It has been determined that burnout syndrome is experienced at a high level in healthcare workers due to the working conditions in the institution they work in and that this situation does not allow the employees to have sufficient job satisfaction (Sivrikaya, 2019). In Özsoy's study (2019), a certain number of employees working in different branches of a private bank were examined. The study examined the effects of the dark characteristics of the employees, narcissism, Machiavellianism and psychopathic characters, on burnout that may occur in the workplace. As a result; it was determined that the narcissism, Machiavellianism and psychopathic characters that the employees received from their managers positively affected and increased burnout (Özsoy, 2019).

CONCLUSION

Generally speaking, burnout syndrome, which starts in the first year of working life in professions where face-to-face relationships are intense, puts the person in a negative mood in organizations. Individuals in a negative mood cannot exist at work and experience problems. From an organizational perspective, these problems end with the action of quitting their job. Considering the expenses incurred by the company during the training of a staff, employees experiencing burnout syndrome constitutes an extra burden for businesses. Therefore, in addition to the measures that individuals should take against burnout syndrome, businesses should also be sensitive about this issue and take the necessary measures for the mental and

physical health of employees. Studies have shown that there are factors such as mobbing, narcissism, and Machiavellianism that trigger burnout, and that burnout is among the factors of events such as intention to leave the job, failure to develop organizational commitment and job satisfaction, and psychologically induced health deterioration. In studies, generally positive and significant relationships have been determined between negative events and burnout. While emotional exhaustion and desensitization, which are sub-dimensions of burnout, are positively and significantly associated, no significant association was observed in the decrease in the sense of personal accomplishment (Öztürk, 2019, Çalışkan and Özkan, 2019, Özutku, 2019). In the studies examined, the relationship between the decrease in the sense of personal accomplishment and burnout is negative. This situation is an indication that people hold the environment responsible for the problems they experience, not themselves. It is thought that the psychology of not accepting that human beings make mistakes is effective in this situation, that both managers and employees do not have a critical perspective, and therefore problems are experienced.

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